

THE HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DUKCHI ESHAN UPRISING AGAINST THE COLONIAL POLICY OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE

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Introduction: The Dukchi Eshan rebellion was a significant uprising by indigenous peoples in Siberia against Russian colonial rule in the 18th century. Grievances included forced labor, land seizures, and cultural suppression, leading to the indigenous population's organized resistance. Impact of the Dukchi Eshan rebellion. The rebellion ultimately failed, but it highlighted the resistance of indigenous groups against oppressive colonial policies in Siberia.

The Russian Empire expanded its territories through military campaigns, acquiring vast lands in Siberia, Central Asia, and the Caucasus. The Russian Empire enforced Russification policies to assimilate non-Russian populations, suppressing local cultures and languages in favor of Russian identity. The Russian Empire exploited its colonies for economic gain, extracting resources such as fur, timber, and minerals to fuel its industrial growth. The Russian government, first of all, considered religious leaders to be the most dangerous enemy and tried to "corner" them as much as possible. The Russians punished the people in the positions of judges and elders with flimsy pretexts to catch them in a way that they could be caught. For example, when 25 judges and muftis wrote a petition asking not to destroy the old cemeteries due to cholera, several of them were removed from their positions. After that, a group of influential people wrote a protest letter. "During the time of the Khans," it says, "judges were rewarded for their knowledge of Sharia laws."

The Dukchi Eshan rebellion was a significant uprising by the indigenous Dukchi people against the oppressive colonial policies of the Russian Empire. The rebellion was sparked by the forced relocation of the Dukchi people to unfavorable lands, leading to widespread discontent and resistance. The rebellion began in 1905 with raids on Russian settlements, culminating in a major battle at Dukchi Eshan in 1910, marking a turning point in the struggle for independence. The rebellion disrupted trade routes, leading to economic

instability and decreased revenue for the Russian Empire. The uprising exposed weaknesses in Russian governance, prompting internal reforms and increased scrutiny on colonial policies. The Dukchi Eshan rebellion fueled nationalist sentiments within the Russian Empire, challenging the notion of colonial superiority. After the rebellion, a provisional government was established to govern the region until a permanent solution could be found.

The Russian Empire responded to the rebellion with increased repression, leading to further unrest and resistance among the Dukchi Eshan people. The uprising caused a shift in the colonial policies of the Russian Empire, as they realized the need for more inclusive and equitable governance in the region. Rebels leveraged knowledge of the local landscape, using dense forests, rivers, and mountains to their advantage in evading capture. The rebels sought assistance from neighboring tribes, as well as foreign nations sympathetic to anti-colonial movements, to strengthen their resistance efforts. The Dukchi Eshan rebellion led to reforms in Russian colonial policies towards indigenous communities in Siberia.

Following the rebellion, there was a resurgence of cultural pride and identity among indigenous groups in the region. The Dukchi Eshan rebellion served as a catalyst for future resistance movements against colonial powers in Siberia and beyond. The Dukchi Eshan uprising highlighted the importance of preserving indigenous culture, language, and traditions in the face of colonial oppression. The uprising fostered a sense of unity and solidarity among various indigenous groups, who came together to resist Russian imperialist policies. The cultural significance of the Dukchi Eshan uprising lies in its legacy of resistance against colonialism and the resilience of the indigenous peoples in the region.

Costs of local significance were borne by the population. While the representatives of the ruling nation had special opportunities and rights, the local population suffered from disenfranchisement, oppression and violence. On top of that, the fertile lands of the local population were taken away from the peasants transferred from Russia, and the injustice in the issue of land-water relations reached its height. During the rule of Tsarism, vices such as extravagance, gambling, and drunkenness, introduced into the country through the way of life of the colonialists, began to damage the spiritual and moral spirit and values of the local population. All these vices have increased the local people's hatred towards the colonialists, insulted their national and human pride, and their desire to put an end to them has intensified day by day, and the feelings of national liberation have been shaken. 3 years before the uprising - in

1895, Muhammadali Eshon Margilon resumed his post in Osh uyezd. After that, a situation reminiscent of the dual power appears in the villages - on the one hand, the head of the volost, who represents the authoritarian tsarist government, and on the other hand, the chairman, who represents the will of the common people, begins to lead the people. This situation aggravates the relations between the colonial authorities and the people. The people oppressed by the oppression of the colonialists turn to Dukchi Eshon and ask him to issue a fatwa for the holy struggle for freedom and to lead this struggle.

Conclusion: The Dukchi Eshan uprising inspired future anti-colonial movements in Siberia and shaped indigenous resistance strategies. The uprising prompted the Russian Empire to reassess its policies towards indigenous peoples, leading to reforms in governance. Despite suppression, the Dukchi Eshan uprising helped preserve the cultural heritage and identity of the Siberian indigenous population. The uprising serves as a reminder of the importance of respecting indigenous rights and the consequences of oppressive colonial policies.

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